

Supporting Information

Balancing Activity and Stability through Compositional Engineering of Ternary PtNi–Au Alloy ORR Catalysts

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Supplementary figures

Figure S1. SEM images of the as-deposited Pt–Ni and PtNi–Au alloy catalysts

Figure S2. Thickness (left axis, red) and roughness (right axis, blue) values calculated from XRR and AFM. XRR-derived thickness and roughness are shown as filled circles, while AFM-derived roughness values are represented by empty circles.

Figure S3. XRD patterns of the as-deposited PtNi–Au, Pt–Ni and monometallic Pt layers

Figure S4. Tafel plots derived from the ORR polarization curves shown in Figure 3c in the vicinity of 0.9 V_{RHE}.

Figure S5. Contact dissolution peak of Pt recorded prior to cycling to different UPLs.

Figure S6. The applied potential protocol along with representative Pt, Ni, and Au dissolution mass-spectrograms taken from PtNi–Au alloy catalysts, as well as the reference PtNi and monometallic Pt electrodes, for 1.0 V_{RHE} UPL. The inset highlights Pt dissolution during the first cycle.

Figure S7. The applied potential protocol along with representative Pt, Ni, and Au dissolution mass-spectrograms taken from PtNi–Au alloy catalysts, as well as the reference PtNi and monometallic Pt electrodes, for 1.2 V_{RHE} UPL. The inset highlights Pt dissolution during the first cycle.

Figure S8. The applied potential protocol along with representative Pt, Ni, and Au dissolution mass-spectrograms taken from PtNi–Au alloy catalysts, as well as the reference PtNi and monometallic Pt electrodes, for 1.5 V_{RHE} UPL.

Calculation of Nickel Monolayer Weight

Regarding leaching from the surface or bulk, we can easily estimate this from ICP-MS results. The weight of a monolayer of Ni per cm^2 can be calculated using the atomic mass of Ni ($58.69 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), Avogadro's number ($6.022 \times 10^{23} \text{ atoms}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) and surface atomic density of Ni (For close-packed (111) planes of face-centered cubic (FCC) nickel, the atomic density is approximately $1.88 \times 10^{15} \text{ atoms}/\text{cm}^2$, considering the area of the unit cell as $S = (\sqrt{3}/2)\times d^2$, and being the atomic diameter for $d = \text{Ni } 0.248 \text{ nm}$). Then

$$m_{\text{Ni}}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2} = \frac{58.69 \text{ g/mol}}{6.022 \times 10^{23} \text{ atoms/mol}} 1.88 \times 10^{15} \text{ atoms}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2} = 185 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2} \quad (\text{Eq. S1})$$

One needs to take into account that:

- Even though the samples contain 40-50 % Ni composition, it is expected that in air, the entire outermost layer of the catalyst would consist of Ni due to its higher affinity for oxygen.¹
- The calculated value of $185 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ is based on the assumption of an ideally flat surface. For rough samples, like those in this study (see AFM images in Figure 1b), it is reasonable to expect a higher value.

References

- (1) Khalakhan, I.; Vega, L.; Vorokhta, M.; Skála, T.; Viñes, F.; Yakovlev, Y. V.; Neyman, K. M.; Matolínová, I. Irreversible Structural Dynamics on the Surface of Bimetallic PtNi Alloy Catalyst under Alternating Oxidizing and Reducing Environments. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* **2020**, *264*, 118476.